

DOWN SYNDROME DISEASE

Abstract : Down syndrome remains the most common chromosomal abnormality in live-born infants in the world today. The association between Down syndrome and congenital heart disease (CHD) is well known, and it is widely recognized that CHD contributes significantly to the morbidity of children with Down syndrome. The reported incidence of CHD in Down syndrome patients is between 40 and 60%. The most commonly described defect is complete atrioventricular septal defect (AVSD), which comprises 30–40% of all cardiac defects. Complex genetic factors are involved. Routine cardiac screening of all newborn babies with Down syndrome is recommended. Expert groups suggest that the cardiac status of all children with Down syndrome should be established by 6 weeks of age to permit appropriate and timely treatment avoiding the establishment of irreversible pulmonary vascular disease that would make corrective surgery impossible.

Keywords : Down syndrome, congenital heart diseases, creening AVSD, pulmonary hypertension.

Introduction

Down syndrome remains the most common chromosomal abnormality in live-born infants in the world today [1]. The association between Down syndrome and congenital heart disease (CHD) is well known. It is widely recognized that CHD contributes significantly to the morbidity and mortality of children with Down syndrome. Despite this there continues to be reports of children with Down syndrome who present with serious CHD too late for the best chance of a good cardiac outcome [2]. Early recognition of lesions is pivotal to obtain the best possible outcome, and

education is still needed. In this chapter, we discuss the incidence and main types of CHD occurring in the setting of Down syndrome. We focus mainly on atrioventricular septal defect (AVSD), which accounts for 30–40% of all cardiac defects in Down syndrome patients. We review genetic consideration and also discuss the principles of surveillance for cardiac disease in this population.

The American Academy of Pediatrics recommends routine cardiac screening of all newborn babies with Down syndrome [13]. This statement is echoed by the Down Syndrome Medical Interest group (DSMIG UK). They recommend that the cardiac status of all children with Down syndrome should be established by 6 weeks of age [2]. Age at evaluation is an important factor for reduction in morbidity and mortality rates. Failure to recognize cardiac defects early in life can have serious consequences including establishment of irreversible pulmonary vascular disease that makes corrective surgery impossible [3]. The fact that children still occasionally present to pediatric cardiology clinics in this fashion indicates that the importance of early detection is not fully acknowledged, even in the present era [9, 14]. Neonatal and infant mortality in patients with Down syndrome remains higher than in the general population, primarily due to CHD [1].

Clinical examination alone remains insufficient to reliably diagnose CHD in Down syndrome with only around 40% of newborns having a cardiovascular abnormality detected based solely on clinical findings [3, 15]. An ECG is likely to be abnormal, particularly in the setting of AVSD, and an abnormal ECG has been shown to have a high positive predictive value for congenital heart disease [3]. Taken together clinical examination and ECG are more powerful than either individually [3].

Pulmonary hypertension in Down syndrome

Patients with Down syndrome are considered to be at higher risk of pulmonary arterial hypertension both with and without CHD. This is likely to be multifactorial, but the high incidence of CHD and airway problems undoubtedly plays a pivotal role

in its development [33]. Down syndrome patients have a high incidence of gastroesophageal reflux with micro-aspiration, recurrent respiratory infections, and sleep apnea. They may experience chronic hypoxia from upper airway obstruction in the form of tracheobronchomalacia, stenosis, or subglottic compromise [33]. There is a high prevalence of persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn in infants with Down syndrome, and as discussed earlier, there is a small subset of Down syndrome CHD patients who continue to have elevated pulmonary vascular resistance beyond the newborn period [16].

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